

Linking Physical Functioning and Psychosocial Factors in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

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Abstract:

Background: Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a prevalent chronic condition that significantly impacts physical functioning and quality of life. Psychosocial factors such as diabetes-related distress and depressive symptoms are known to affect the health outcomes of individuals with T2DM, but the interplay between these factors and physical functioning needs further exploration. This study aims to investigate the association between physical functioning and psychosocial factors in patients with T2DM, with the goal of informing comprehensive management strategies.

Methods: 150 Participants completed the Short Form-36 (SF-36) to assess physical functioning, the Diabetes Distress Scale (DDS) to measure diabetes-related distress, and the Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) to evaluate depressive symptoms. Pearson correlation coefficients and multiple regression analysis were used to analyze the data, controlling for age, gender, duration of diabetes, and comorbidities. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The mean SF-36 physical functioning score was 65.4, indicating moderate physical functioning. Significant negative correlations were found between physical functioning and both DDS ($r = -0.52$, $p < 0.001$) and PHQ-9 ($r = -0.47$, $p < 0.001$) scores. Multiple regression analysis revealed that higher diabetes-related distress ($\beta = -0.35$, $p < 0.001$) and depressive symptoms ($\beta = -0.29$, $p < 0.001$) were significant independent predictors of poorer physical functioning, alongside age and duration of diabetes.

Conclusion: The study highlights a significant association between poorer physical functioning and higher levels of diabetes-related distress and depressive symptoms in patients with T2DM. These findings underscore the importance of addressing psychosocial factors in the management of T2DM.

Recommendations: Healthcare providers should incorporate psychological assessments and interventions into routine diabetes care to improve physical functioning and overall well-being in patients with T2DM. Further research should focus on developing and evaluating integrated care models that address both physical and psychosocial aspects of diabetes management.

Keywords: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Physical Functioning, Diabetes-Related Distress, Depressive Symptoms, Psychosocial Factors.

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Introduction

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by insulin resistance and hyperglycemia, significantly impacting global public health. The prevalence of T2DM has been steadily rising, with the International Diabetes Federation estimating that 463 million adults were living with diabetes in 2019, a number expected to rise to 700 million by 2045 [1]. This increasing burden necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing the health and well-being of individuals with T2DM.

Physical functioning, defined as the ability to perform activities of daily living, is a critical component of overall health in patients with T2DM. Impaired physical functioning in these patients can lead to decreased quality of life, increased risk of complications, and higher healthcare utilization [2]. Recent studies have highlighted that individuals with T2DM often experience reduced physical functioning compared to non-diabetic counterparts, largely due to diabetes-related complications such as neuropathy, retinopathy, and cardiovascular diseases [3].

Psychosocial factors, including diabetes-related distress and depressive symptoms, are increasingly recognized as significant determinants of physical health in patients with T2DM. Diabetes-related distress refers to the emotional burden and worries specific to managing diabetes and its complications. It has been found to affect 36-40% of individuals with T2DM, impacting their self-care behaviors and glycemic control [4]. Similarly, depressive symptoms are prevalent among T2DM patients, with meta-analyses suggesting that the prevalence of depression is nearly twice as high in people with diabetes compared to those without.

The interplay between physical functioning and psychosocial factors in T2DM is complex and multifaceted. Evidence suggests that higher levels of diabetes-related distress and depressive symptoms are associated with poorer physical functioning. This relationship can create a vicious cycle, where poor physical health exacerbates psychological distress, further impairing physical functioning [5]. Understanding these associations is crucial for developing holistic and effective interventions aimed at improving the overall health outcomes of individuals with T2DM. Despite the growing recognition of the importance of psychosocial factors, there is a need for more research to elucidate the specific pathways through which they influence physical functioning in T2DM patients.

This study aims to investigate the association between physical functioning and psychosocial factors in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional study.

Participants: A total of 150 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus were included in this study. Participants were recruited from the outpatient diabetes clinic of the hospital.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus for at least one year.
2. Aged between 30 and 75 years.
3. Able to provide informed consent.
4. Stable medication regimen for the past three months.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Presence of severe diabetic complications (e.g., end-stage renal disease, proliferative retinopathy).
2. Diagnosed with other chronic conditions that severely impact physical functioning (e.g., severe osteoarthritis).

3. Cognitive impairments that interfere with the ability to complete questionnaires.
4. Pregnant women.
5. Patients currently participating in another clinical trial.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from the outpatient clinic registry. Information bias was addressed by training data collectors and using validated tools for data collection. Confounding factors were controlled through statistical adjustments.

Data Collection: Data were collected using structured interviews and validated questionnaires. The primary tools included:

- Short Form-36 (SF-36) for assessing physical functioning.
- Diabetes Distress Scale (DDS) for evaluating diabetes-related psychosocial stress.
- Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) for assessing depressive symptoms.
- Sociodemographic and clinical data were also collected through medical record reviews.

Procedure: Eligible participants were identified and approached during their routine clinic visits. After obtaining informed consent, trained research assistants conducted face-to-face interviews to collect data. Participants completed the SF-36, DDS, and PHQ-9 questionnaires. Medical records were reviewed to extract relevant clinical data.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics. The association between physical functioning (SF-36 scores) and psychosocial factors (DDS and PHQ-9 scores) was assessed using Pearson correlation coefficients. Multiple regression analysis was performed to control for potential confounders such as age, sex, duration of diabetes, and comorbidities. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

The study included 150 participants with type 2 diabetes mellitus. The mean age of the participants was 58.3 years (SD = 10.2), with 55% being female. The average duration of diabetes was 8.5 years (SD = 6.1). Table 1 summarizes the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study participants.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Variable	Value
Mean Age (years)	58.3 ± 10.2
Gender, n (%)	
- Male	67 (45%)
- Female	83 (55%)
Mean Duration of diabetes (years)	8.5 ± 6.1
Mean HbA1c (%)	7.8 ± 1.2
Comorbidities, n (%)	
- Hypertension	65 (43.3%)
- Dyslipidemia	45 (30%)
- Cardiovascular disease	25 (16.7%)

The mean SF-36 physical functioning score was 65.4 (SD = 22.3), indicating a moderate level of physical functioning among participants. The mean DDS score was 2.4 (SD = 0.9), reflecting moderate diabetes-related distress. The mean PHQ-9 score was 7.3 (SD = 4.8), indicating mild depressive symptoms.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for SF-36, DDS, and PHQ-9 Scores

Measure	Mean (SD)
SF-36 Physical Functioning	65.4 (22.3)
Diabetes Distress Scale (DDS)	2.4 (0.9)
Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9)	7.3 (4.8)

Pearson correlation coefficients were computed to assess the relationships between physical functioning and psychosocial factors. The results indicated a significant negative correlation between SF-36 physical functioning scores and DDS scores ($r = -0.52$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that higher diabetes-related distress is associated with lower

physical functioning. Similarly, there was a significant negative correlation between SF-36 physical functioning scores and PHQ-9 scores ($r = -0.47$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that higher depressive symptoms are associated with lower physical functioning.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Coefficients

Measure	SF-36 Physical Functioning
Diabetes Distress Scale (DDS)	-0.52
Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9)	-0.47

Multiple regression analysis was conducted to examine the independent effects of diabetes-related distress and depressive symptoms on physical functioning while controlling for age, gender, duration of diabetes, and comorbidities. The overall model was significant ($F = 15.2$, $p < 0.001$) and explained 45% of the variance in physical functioning ($R^2 = 0.45$).

The results showed that both diabetes-related distress ($\beta = -0.35$, $p < 0.001$) and depressive symptoms ($\beta = -0.29$, $p < 0.001$) were significant independent predictors of physical functioning. Age ($\beta = -0.18$, $p = 0.01$) and duration of diabetes ($\beta = -0.15$, $p = 0.03$) also had significant negative associations with physical functioning. Gender and comorbidities were not significant predictors in the model.

Table 4: Multiple Regression Analysis Predicting Physical Functioning

Predictor	B	SE	β	p-value
Age	-0.45	0.18	-0.18	0.01
Gender (Female)	-2.10	3.45	-0.05	0.54
Duration of diabetes	-0.38	0.18	-0.15	0.03
Comorbidities (presence)	-1.78	2.87	-0.04	0.54
Diabetes Distress Scale (DDS)	-8.75	2.02	-0.35	<0.001
Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9)	-1.45	0.34	-0.29	<0.001

Discussion

The study explored the relationship between physical functioning and psychosocial factors in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, involving 150 participants. The demographic and clinical characteristics indicated a balanced gender

distribution, with an average age of 58.3 years and an average diabetes duration of 8.5 years. A significant proportion of participants had comorbidities such as hypertension, dyslipidemia, and cardiovascular disease.

The analysis revealed that the average SF-36 physical functioning score was 65.4, indicating a moderate level of physical functioning among the participants. The Diabetes Distress Scale (DDS) and Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) scores averaged 2.4 and 7.3, respectively, suggesting moderate diabetes-related distress and mild depressive symptoms. These psychosocial factors were found to be significantly correlated with physical functioning. Specifically, higher diabetes-related distress and depressive symptoms were associated with lower physical functioning scores.

Pearson correlation analysis confirmed significant negative correlations between physical functioning and both DDS ($r = -0.52$, $p < 0.001$) and PHQ-9 ($r = -0.47$, $p < 0.001$) scores. This indicates that patients experiencing greater distress and depressive symptoms tend to have poorer physical functioning. These findings highlight the interconnectedness of physical and mental health in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Further, multiple regression analysis demonstrated that diabetes-related distress and depressive symptoms were independent predictors of physical functioning, even after controlling for age, gender, duration of diabetes, and comorbidities. The model explained 45% of the variance in physical functioning, with diabetes-related distress ($\beta = -0.35$, $p < 0.001$) and depressive symptoms ($\beta = -0.29$, $p < 0.001$) emerging as significant predictors. Age and duration of diabetes also had significant negative associations with physical functioning, whereas gender and comorbidities were not significant predictors.

These results underscore the importance of addressing psychosocial factors in the clinical management of type 2 diabetes. The significant impact of diabetes-related distress and depressive symptoms on physical functioning suggests that comprehensive diabetes care should include psychological support and interventions aimed at reducing distress and managing depressive symptoms. This holistic approach could potentially improve the overall health and quality of life for patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

A study investigated the associations between physical functioning (PhF) and psychosocial factors (PsF) in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). The cross-sectional study involved 140 patients and assessed various measures of PhF and PsF. Results indicated significant associations between high exercise self-efficacy (ESE) and physical functioning measures such as Activities of Daily Living (ADL) (OR = 2.20, 95%CI = 1.12-4.14; $p = 0.026$), Hand Grip Strength (HGS) (OR = 2.85, 95%CI = 2.58-3.12; $p = 0.012$), and 6-Minute Walk Distance (6-MWD) (OR = 2.96, 95%CI = 1.91-4.58; $p = 0.003$). High

perceived exercise benefit (PEB) was also significantly associated with improved PhF measures (ADL: OR = 2.41, 95%CI = 1.27-4.57; $p = 0.017$) [6].

A systematic review examined the relationships among psychosocial determinants and coping in adults with T2DM. The review synthesized findings from 22 quantitative studies and identified anxiety, depression, stress, and diabetes distress as key influential psychosocial factors. Increased social support was inversely related to emotional distress and positively related to coping styles, which were associated with improved psychological and physical health outcomes. Problem-focused coping was particularly linked to better health outcomes [7].

Another study assessed the impact of personality functioning on glucose regulation in T2DM patients. The study found that levels of personality functioning were associated with baseline HbA1c levels, but not with the decline in HbA1c over time. Depression did not predict changes in glucose regulation, highlighting the importance of personality factors in managing T2DM [8].

A study examined the prevalence of depression and the associated physical and psychosocial factors in adults with T2DM. The study included 421 patients and found that the likelihood of depression increased with higher levels of pain and ambulation difficulties, as well as with an increased number of traumatic events and socioeconomic stressors. Conversely, higher self-esteem was associated with a decreased likelihood of depression [9].

Furthermore, a study assessed the association of psychological variables with physical activity and sedentary behavior in men and women with T2DM. The study found that physical activity was significantly associated with higher social support in women and increased self-efficacy in men. Sedentary time was associated with higher perceived interference, anxiety, and depressive symptoms, and reduced diabetes self-efficacy in women, while it was associated solely with anxiety in men [10].

Conclusion

The study found significant associations between physical functioning and psychosocial factors in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. Higher levels of diabetes-related distress and depressive symptoms were linked to poorer physical functioning. These findings underscore the importance of addressing psychosocial factors in the management of physical health in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this

study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: Healthcare providers should incorporate psychological assessments and interventions into routine diabetes care to improve physical functioning and overall well-being in patients with T2DM. Further research should focus on developing and evaluating integrated care models that address both physical and psychosocial aspects of diabetes management.

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